

Digital Distractions or Learning Tools? Rethinking Technology in Early Language Classrooms

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Abstract

The COVID-19 pandemic has led to a sharp increase in the use of technology in primary education, significantly impacting young language learners' classrooms. This surge in the use of technology in children's classrooms has raised concerns among primary school educators about the impact of increased screen time and digital distractions on additional language acquisition. Preliminary discussions with primary school teachers and student teachers in Madrid, Spain, highlight a growing dependence on technology in children's language classrooms. While the immediate effects of the pandemic continue to wane, this reliance continues to grow. The findings of this study indicate that while technology can support personalised learning, its overuse risks distracting students and hindering language acquisition. This paper emphasises the urgent need for research on the effects of classroom technology on young language learners and promotes a balanced approach to its integration. By examining the experiences of educators in Madrid, this study offers insights into local challenges and strategies that may be adaptable to other regions and broader educational contexts.

Keywords: post-pandemic, young language learners, technology integration, screen time, digital distraction